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Recent updates on the synthesis of Dihydroquinolines: A review**K. Premalathaa**

Department of Chemistry, University College for women, Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

M.Kavitha

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

V.Shashikala

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana, India

Corresponding author email: premasheshu@gmail.com

Abstract--- Compounds containing quinoline and dihydroquinoline backbone are very important compounds due to their wide range of applications in pharmacy and medicine. Dihydroquinolines, derivatives of quinolines play a very important role in the development of various types of newer drugs and it can be used as lead compounds for future investigation in the field of drug discovery process. Dihydroquinolines are widely used as scaffolds in the synthesis of new heterocyclic systems. The present review provides a first full literature overview on the synthetic methods in the dihydroquinoline synthesis. The review deals with the general method of condensation as well as recent advancements in the synthesis of 1,2-dihydroquinolines under different conditions like microwave, multicomponent synthesis (MCR), ultrasound promoted synthesis, metal catalyzed synthesis, solvent-free synthesis, acid catalyzed synthesis, nanocatalyst synthesis and other important synthetic methods.

Keywords--- Dihydroquinolines, microwave, multicomponent, and ultrasound, metal catalyzed synthesis, and solvent free synthesis, acid catalyzed synthesis.

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Introduction

Importance of Technology

The heterocyclic compounds containing nitrogen are the key frame work in many essential natural and synthetic products [1,2]. Most of the nitrogen heterocycles are present in nature in living cells [3], alkaloids, hormones [4] and amino acids and hence they constitute a large fraction of medicinal and industrial chemistry. They are the building blocks for synthesis of the pharmaceutical active compounds in the organic chemistry. Among the N-heterocyclic compounds, Quinoline is well known for its diverse biological activities. Quinoline and its derivatives are found in many biologically active compounds and are of importance as they have various biological and pharmaceutical activities such as antimalarial, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-asthmatic, anti-hypertensive, and tyrosine kinase inhibiting properties [5-8]. Dihydroquinolines are the heterocyclic compounds which has versatile applications in the synthetic organic chemistry and among the isomeric dihydroquinolines, 1,2-dihydroquinolines have received substantial attention due to their potential biological activities and also due to their usefulness as precursors for other biologically active compounds. In addition, substrates possessing dihydroquinoline motif have been used as lipid peroxidation inhibitors, HMG-CoA reductase inhibitors, ileal bile acid transporter inhibitors and progesterone agonists and antagonists [9] They can be readily transformed to 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinolines and quinolines which are of great value in medicinal chemistry [10-11].

Chemistry of Dihydroquinolines

Dihydroquinolines are the N-heterocyclic compounds which contains a benzene ring fused with dihydropyridine ring. The dihydroquinolines known are 1,2-dihydroquinolines, 1,4-dihydroquinolines and 3,4-dihydroquinolines, 1,2-dihydroquinolines are most studied and 3,4-dihydroquinolines are the least studied among the isomeric structures.

This article highlights the different approaches for the synthesis of dihydroquinolines. Here, in this review, the synthesis of dihydroquinolines using various synthetic techniques like microwave (MW), ultrasound, multicomponent reactions (MCR), metal catalysed, solvent free and nano catalyst synthesis are discussed

Dihydroquinoline Synthesis under different conditions

The most general approach for the synthesis of dihydroquinolines is Skraup cyclization which involves the condensation of anilines with glycerol in the presence of concentrated sulfuric acid [12] [Scheme 1,2].

Synthesis of Dihydroquinolines under different conditions

Scheme 1: General reaction of Skraup synthesis

Scheme 2: Reaction mechanism of Skraup synthesis

The modified skraup cyclization involves the heating a mixture of aniline with two molecules of acetone in the presence of iodine as catalyst resulting in the formation of 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2-dihydroquinoline [13] [Scheme 3,4]. The first step is the aldol condensation of the ketone forming α,β -unsaturated ketone, which readily undergoes addition with arylamines. It is followed by the intramolecular cyclization and subsequent dehydration results in the dihydroquinoline formation.

Scheme 3: General reaction of modified skraup synthesis

Scheme 4: Reaction mechanism of modified Skraup synthesis

Microwave Synthesis:

Microwave (MW) synthesis has recently been considered as a powerful tool in organic synthesis, and medicinal chemistry for the design and construction of pharmaceutically important compounds. The advantages of microwave irradiation over conventional heating are shorter reaction time, higher yield under milder conditions, neat reactions, higher purity of the products formed, and suppression of by-product formation. These features make microwave assisted reactions greener and environment-friendly process.

Ranu and coworkers [14] [Scheme 5] developed a new microwave-assisted (MW) route for dihydroquinoline synthesis from substituted anilines and a β -disubstituted alkyl vinyl ketone on the surface of silica gel impregnated with indium(III) chloride without any-solvent. A wide range of substituted anilines and structurally diverse alkyl vinyl ketones were subjected to this procedure to produce the corresponding dihydroquinolines in high yields.

Scheme 5

Gültekin et.al [15] [Scheme 6] have reported the synthesis of Substituted 1,2-dihydroquinolines from substituted anilines and methyl pyruvate using catalytic amounts of $\text{Bi}(\text{OTf})_3$ as a catalyst under microwave-assisted conditions. The reaction provides 1,2-dihydroquinolines in good yields. This method is simple, easy to work up, inexpensive, with a broad substrate scope and short reaction times

Scheme 6

A mild and efficient solvent-free method has been developed for the synthesis of dihydroquinoline derivatives by one-pot reaction of anilines with alkyl vinyl ketones using stable and effective heterogeneous catalyst potassium dodecatungstocobaltate (25 mol %) (PDTC) under microwave irradiation in high yields by Bose and co-authors [16] [Scheme 7].

Scheme 7

Ultrasonication synthesis:

Ultrasonic assisted organic synthesis as a green and ecofriendly synthetic approach is a powerful technique which is being used more and more to accelerate organic reactions [17]. These reactions are more advantageous over the traditional thermal methods as large number of organic reactions can be carried out in higher yields, shorter reaction times, and milder conditions etc.

Sreekantha et.al [18] [Scheme 8] reported Catalyst-free ultrasound assisted protocol for the condensation of malononitrile, 2-naphthol/resorcinol, aldehydes, and ammonium acetate in aqueous medium at 60 °C to afford a wide range of valuable dihydroquinolines in high yields with short reaction times of 60–90 min.

Scheme 8:

MCR Synthesis:

Multicomponent reactions have attracted a great attention in recent times due to their simplicity, atom economy, and greater efficiency due to reduction in the number of intermediate purifications where by the yield of the products increases. These reactions are very useful for the generation of a variety of heterocyclic compounds in one-pot from simple and inexpensive starting materials [19].

Tamariz and coworkers [20] [Scheme 9] described a highly efficient and regioselective synthesis of 1,2-dihydroquinolines through a multicomponent reaction between aniline and two ketones. The reaction is catalyzed by magnesium bromide under solvent free conditions. Variety of anilines and ketones including cyclic ketones were evaluated forming a series of 1,2-dihydroquinolines with diverse substitution patterns.

Scheme 9:

A one-pot quick and efficient multicomponent reaction for the synthesis of a new series of functionalized 8-hydroxy-4-phenyl-1,2-dihydroquinoline derivatives using 30 mol% ammonium acetate in ethanol as solvent has been developed by Tabassum and co-authors [21] [Scheme 10].

Scheme 10:

Metal Catalysed Synthesis:

Metal-catalyzed reactions play an important role in the synthesis of natural products and bioactive substances. Metal catalysts are abundant, easy to prepare, and inexpensive. Now a days, the use of metal catalysts in the preparation of heterocyclic compounds has become very attractive as these metal catalysts can be easily separated from the reaction mixture by simple filtration, and can also be

recycled. Metal-catalyzed reactions minimize the formation waste and are in general environmentally friendly. Organometallic reagents play a significant role in metal catalysis [22].

Kamiguchi et.al [23] [Scheme 11] reported the synthesis of 1,2-dihydro-2,2,4-trimethylquinoline from aniline and acetone. The reaction was studied in a gas-phase over halide clusters as solid acid catalysts. After activation of a niobium halide cluster, $[(\text{Nb}_6\text{Cl}_{12})\text{Cl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which has an octahedral metal framework, at an elevated temperature in a hydrogen stream for 1 h, reaction was initiated by introduction of stoichiometric amounts of aniline and acetone at the activation temperature. The catalysis to yield product became evident above 200 °C. Both the catalytic activity of catalyst and the selectivity for product increased with increasing temperature, having a local maximum at 300 °C. The chloride clusters of tantalum with the same metal framework and rhenium with a triangular metal framework also catalyzed the condensation. Thus, a halide cluster can be a substitute for liquid acid, particularly at high temperatures.

Scheme 11:

A domino Rh and Pd catalysed synthesis of dihydroquinolines was described by Lei Zhang and coworkers [24] [Scheme 12]. Two metals and two ligands are placed in one reaction vessel along with the two reactive reagents to afford selective coupling which results in the formation of dihydroquinolines. The reactivity and relative catalyst ligand loadings were also studied.

Scheme 12:

Arcadi and co-authors [25] [Scheme 13] reported a Au(I)-catalyzed synthetic route to functionalized 1,2-dihydroquinolines. This novel approach is based on the use of N-ethoxycarbonyl protected-N-propargylanilines as building blocks that rapidly undergo the intramolecular hydroarylation reaction affording the 6-endo cyclization product in good to high yields.

Scheme 13:

A cobalt catalyzed annulation of anilides with allenes to synthesize 1,2-dihydroquinolines is described by Cheng and coauthors[26] [Scheme 14]. The reaction proceeds by C-H activation, allene insertion followed by β -hydride elimination and an intramolecular 1,4-addition to a butadiene group containing intermediate.

Scheme 14:

Fig 6: The ECG representation after treatment

Heterogenous catalytic condensation of aniline with acetone was employed to synthesize 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2-dihydroquinolines by Krishna and Sounak Roy [27] [Scheme 15]. Zn^{2+} -, Sn^{2+} -, and Cu^{2+} -exchanged tungstophosphoric acid (TPA) supported on $\gamma-Al_2O_3$ was synthesized by microwave hydrothermal method and the synthesized catalyst was characterized by XRD, Raman, FE-SEM etc and was used for the condensation reaction.

Scheme 15:

Solvent free synthesis:

Solvent free protocols are not only more environmentally benign but also more economically feasible. Solvent free reactions have many advantages over the reactions carried in solvents like reduced pollution, low costs, and simplicity in process and handling, hence solvent free reactions gained lot of importance in the organic transformations [28].

Ballini and co authors [29] [Scheme 16] found that neutral alumina carries out the solvent free reaction of 2-aminobenzaldehyde over a range of nitroalkenes, under mild and convenient conditions, allowing the one pot synthesis of 3-nitro-1,2-dihydroquinolines. This method has several advantages such as short reaction times, no excess of the reactants are demanded, no solvent is employed, cheap catalyst is applied, three steps can be performed one-pot, mild and neutral reaction conditions, no work up needed, since the crude mixture was directly charged to a chromatographic column for immediate purification. Thus, this method shows very important advantages from both ecological and economic point of view.

Scheme 16:

Kundu and coworkers [30] [Scheme 17] developed an efficient process for the synthesis of 2,2,4-trisubstituted-1,2-dihydroquinolines in good yields through a simple one-pot condensation between anilines and ketones under solvent-free conditions in the presence of zinc triflate as a catalyst at room temperature.

Scheme 17:

one-pot synthesis of 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2-dihydroquinolines by the reaction of anilines with acetone or desired ketone under solvent free conditions was developed using MOF-199 as catalyst by Raut et al. [31] [Scheme 18]. This procedure is an efficient, mild, and convenient.

Scheme 18:

Acid catalysed synthesis:

Nowadays, many organic reactions are conducted under acid catalysed conditions because of their unique reactivity, mild reaction conditions and low cost they give easy accessibility for the synthesis of a wide range of organic compounds [32].

Edwards and co-workers [33] [Scheme 19] studied the BF₃•OEt₂-mediated reaction of 2-isopropenylaniline with a variety of ketones to form 2,2,4-trisubstituted 1,2-dihydroquinolines. Treatment of 2-isopropenylaniline with a number of different ketones in the presence of BF₃•OEt₂ in toluene at elevated temperatures afforded cleanly and in moderate to excellent yields the requisite 2,2,4-trisubstituted dihydroquinolines. Sterically hindered and/or cyclopropyl ketones failed to afford the desired products.

Scheme 19:

A mild, convenient, and efficient process has been developed for the synthesis of 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,2-dihydroquinolines by the reaction of anilines with acetone catalyzed by ytterbium(III) triflate [Yb(OTf)₃] in ionic liquids by Yongshu Li et.al [34] [Scheme 20]. The authors also investigated the effect of different ionic liquids like [bpy][BF₄] (bpy = 1-butylpyridine), [bmim][BF₄] (bmim = 1-butyl-3-methyl imidazolium), and [bmim][PF₆] and [bmim][BF₄] was chosen as the reaction's solvent as highest yields was observed with it. The catalyst and ionic liquids can be easily recovered and reused, making this method friendly and environmentally acceptable.

Scheme 20:

Kamakshi and B.S.R.Reddy [35] [Scheme 21] reported the synthesis of substituted 2,2,4-dihydroquinolines from anilines and acetone and methyl ethyl ketone using silicotungstic acid as the catalyst in good yields. The authors also screened the effect of varied temperature (RT, 50 °C and 70 °C) and solvents (CHCl₃, CH₃CN, H₂O, H₂O/EtOH and toluene) on the reaction. It was observed that acetonitrile was the best solvent in promoting the reaction. The optimum catalyst amount for achieving very good yields was found to be five percent. The reactions were clean and the products isolated with minimal work-up are the important advantages of this protocol. The reaction yields were found to be higher for anilines with electron withdrawing groups rather than the electron donating groups.

Scheme 21:

Coupling of Aryl amines with 2,2-dimethoxypropane (2,2-DMP) in the presence of 5 mol% of bismuth triflate under solvent-free conditions to produce 1,2-dihydroquinolines in high yields under mild conditions was reported by J.S.Yadav and co-authors [36] [Scheme 22].

Scheme 22:

Ji-Chen Zhang and Jian-Xin Ji [37] [Scheme 23] designed a simple and efficient method for the synthesis of polysubstituted 1,2-dihydroquinolines via an indium(III) catalysed tandem reaction of α -ketoesters with primary or secondary amines. The reactions of pyruvate with amines showed superior catalytic activity with (1 mol %) of indium triflate, whereas the reactions of α -alkyl substituted ketoesters and arylamines proceeded smoothly in (10 mol %) of indium triflate. Here, In(OTf)₃ is a mild, inexpensive, easily available, non-toxic, and highly efficient catalyst.

Scheme 23:

Yadav and coworkers [38] [Scheme 24] reported an optimized and efficient process for the synthesis of 2, 2, 4-Trimethyl-1, 2- dihydroquinoline from an acid- catalyzed Skraup Cyclization of acetone and aniline using Polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane functionalized with sulfonic acid group [POSS-SO₃H] as an acid catalyst which is synthesized by self-assembly of silane precursor (i.e) 3-mercaptopropyl trimethoxy silane without using any solvent. Shorter reaction time, synthesis of new acidic catalyst with characterization studies, solvent free conditions and high yields are the additional features of this synthesis.

Scheme 24:

A facile and efficient iron-catalyzed intramolecular allylic amination of 2-aminophenyl-1-en-3-ols proceeded smoothly to afford 1,2-dihydroquinoline derivatives under mild reaction conditions with good yields was reported by Zhiming Wang et al [39] [Scheme 25].

Scheme 25:

Hajare et al [40] [Scheme 26] developed a simple, convenient and efficient p-toluenesulfonic acid catalyzed tandem reaction of aliphatic ketones with substituted anilines towards the synthesis of polysubstituted 1,2-dihydroquinolines. The ready availability of the catalyst, operational simplicity, cost effectiveness of the process and excellent regioselectivity are the remarkable advantages of this methodology.

Scheme 26:

A series of novel dihydroquinoline derivatives were synthesized using malononitrile, 2-aminobenzamide, and benzaldehydes in the presence of a catalytic amount of acetic acid, without the use of any additional cocatalyst under solvent-free conditions by Elham Kanaani and Masoud Nasr-Esfahani [41] [Scheme 27]. The reaction is characterized by high efficiency, easy workup, simple purification of the products, and availability of catalyst.

Scheme 27:

Nanocatalyst synthesis:

Nanocatalysts find wide applications due to their activity at nano scale and they have a high surface-to-volume ratio and active sites that display high activity and selectivity in the synthesis of various heterocyclic compounds. Nanocatalysts are easily prepared, recyclable, and show clean reaction, excellent yields in short reaction time, simple separation, and reduce the use of toxic solvents and reagents [42].

El-Remaily and coworkers [43] [Scheme 27], have investigated the catalytic activity of TiO₂ NPs in the synthesis of 1,2-dihydroquinoline derivatives with excellent yields and low cost. TiO₂ nanoparticles (TiO₂ NPs) was synthesized using Neem leaf extract. This is simple, rapid, eco-friendly, cheaper and green tools for TiO₂ NPs synthesis using agricultural waste at lower applied temperature. Characterization of the extracted TiO₂ NPs was confirmed by XRD, SEM, EDAX, TEM, HR-TEM, SAED, and FT-IR, respectively. Purification of the synthesized 1,2-dihydroquinoline derivatives carried out by easy work-up of non-chromatographic methods.

Scheme 27:

Other methods:

Dihydroquinolines are also prepared by various other methods such as ring closing metathesis, reduction of quinolines, zeolite catalysed synthesis etc.

The synthesis of 1,2-dihydroquinolines by the hydrazine-catalysed ring-closing carbonyl-olefin metathesis (RCCOM) of N-allylated 2-aminobenzaldehydes is developed by Zhang et.al [44] [Scheme 28]. A variety of substrates with different substitution patterns are reported.

Scheme 28:

An efficient conversion of quinolines to 1,2-dihydroquinolines was developed using sodium cyanoborohydride as a reductant by Qing-Feng and coauthors [45] [Scheme 29]. A series of N-alkoxycarbonyl-1,2-dihydroquinolines were obtained through reduction of activated quinolium salts.

Scheme 29:

A new, environmentally-friendly synthesis of dihydroquinolines from aniline and ketones using a small pore size zeolite as catalyst is described by Adrienn Hegedus et.al.[46] [Scheme 30]. This method is simple, cheap and gives the dihydroquinolines in high yield.

Scheme 30:**Conclusions:**

Dihydroquinolines and its derivatives play a significant role in the organic synthesis and medicinal chemistry. As per literature study, this will be the first and only review that critically discusses synthesis of Dihydroquinolines. In this article, we have systematically reviewed the various synthetic approaches of dihydroquinolines using different environmental conditions such as MW-assisted synthesis, acid-catalyzed, solvent free synthesis, nano-catalyzed, and, etc., This review will be very useful to the researcher working in this field, and it would help them to develop a new eco-friendly, green and economical methods.

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